

**FROM THE HISTORY OF THE ELECTORAL LAW OF THE REPUBLIC OF
UZBEKISTAN (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE CONSTITUTIONS
OF TURKISTAN ASSR, KHOREZM KHSR, BUKHARA KHSR AND
UZBEKISTAN SSR)**

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Annotation: The article covers the history of the constitutions that existed before the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In it, the main attention was paid to the sections related to elections in the constitutions, the issues related to political aspects of the existing system and periods, election processes were analyzed. There is also information about the SYNO relations in the constitutions.

Keywords: the Constitution, the Soviet government, the Congress, the Soviet of people's ministers, elections, deprivation of the right to vote, vote, are unjust.

Each child of the country comes from the jewelers of the history of his homeland to carefully study all the realities associated with his past. Therefore, the deep and objective coverage of the history of the past events, the fate of our compatriots and the history of the roads that were passed before we reached such light-days is our main duty before our people.

With the information we bring below, we try to illuminate the political aspects of the existing system and periods in our independent homeland, focusing our main attention on the sections of the history of the constitutions that have been applied so far in relation to the system of elections.

The Constitution is the Basic Law of the state, which determines the structure of the state, the system of government and administration, the order of their competence and formation, the electoral system, the rights and freedoms of citizens, as well as the judicial system. In other words, the Constitution is the basis of all existing laws and the most basic sign of statehood¹.

The Supreme bodies of the Union were responsible for regulating all important directions of the foreign and domestic policy of the state, including the representation of the USSR in international relations, the issue of changing external borders, the adoption of new republics into the Union, the leadership of the Armed Forces².

¹ Abduvaliev N. The order of entry" legal and legal basis of the development of our country " [electronic resource]: https://parliament.gov.uz/uz/events/opinion/33013/?sphrase_id=7862922).

² YouTube – (614) 1 History of the Constitution of Russia

However, in this Constitution, no information on the electoral system, the procedure for conducting elections, the right to elect or the deprivation of the right to elect has been brought. These processes were later reflected in the constitutions of the Allied Republics.

Another notable aspect is that after the adoption of the first Constitution of the USSR, new constitutional processes immediately began throughout the Allied Republics. If one does not pay attention to the fact that the previous constitutions of some allied Republics remained in practice until 1926-1927, the constitutional gap in the intermediate period is close to reality when it is said to have been observed.

The first draft constitution in the history of the Uzbek SSR was approved on March 27-11, 1927 in the II Congress of the Soviets of the Umumo'zbekistan and published on July 11. In this Constitution, as in the constitutions of other Union republics, the powers of state power are defined as "deputies of the Soviets of working peasants and red soldiers". Uzbekistan included the Autonomous Republic of Tajikistan. Tajikistan ASSR was given a lot of powers, and a special section was devoted to the relations between them.

In order for the USSR to make the republics of its composition more centralized, it has always assumed that disputes between them, starting from their constitutions and laws, are also in their own policy. The Tajik ASSR, included in the structure of Uzbekistan, was given the right to form the composition of the people's commissars' Soviet and to make changes to it at any time, the rights to enter into force after the re-consideration of the laws adopted by the Uzbek SSR and many other powers³.

It was noted that Chapters 8 and 9 of Chapter 6 of the Constitution are devoted to elections to Soviets and their organization, a detailed list of categories of citizens who have the right to elect and be elected in elections and who are deprived of these rights is determined by the decrees issued on the basis of this Constitution, as well as decisions

In 1931, in connection with the separation of Tajikistan ASSR from the structure of the Uzbek SSR, Tajikistan was re-published with amendments to the Constitution. However, the issue of restoring the right of citizens deprived of voting rights in both constitutions has not been established [28. P.30]. Only in the programs of the NCC of the Uzbek SSR "on elections to the Shura" on December 12, 1927 and "on elections to the Soviets of the Uzbek SSR" on

³ From the history of the constitutions adopted in the past of Uzbekistan.
[Electronic resource] access procedure: <https://teznews.uz/08-12-2020/>

December 12, 1929, citizens who did not use their electoral rights were given a description, and the procedures for restoring their rights were shown.

In particular, as former police officers, prison officials and others (Article 38 of this program is presented in paragraphs "m" and "l"), it was established that persons deprived of electoral rights in accordance with paragraphs "a", "b", "v", "g" and "D" of Article 93 of the Constitution of the USSR of Uzbekistan, if they are currently engaged in productive and socially useful labor and have proved their loyalty⁴.

In the autumn of 1935 year, the central executive branch of the USSR for the development of a new edition of the Constitution of the USSR, which should reflect the idea of the victory of socialism I.V. Under the chairmanship of Stalin, he formed the Constitutional Commission. On June 12, 1936, the draft constitution was published, and for six months it was discussed in the Republican Congress of Soviets from the meetings of workers at all levels of enterprises.

On December 5, 1936, at the VIII extraordinary congress of the Soviets, a new Constitution of the USSR was adopted and this document was sealed with the name "Stalin Constitution" in history⁵.

Theses on the leading role of the Communist Party in the Constitution were strengthened, norms were introduced that laid down the economic foundations of socialism, new chapters were introduced in relation to the Constitution in 1924 - the social structure, local government bodies, the judiciary and the prosecutor's office, the basic rights and obligations of citizens, the electoral system and the right to vote (It also abolished all restrictions on electoral rights enshrined in previous constitutions, indicating that the right to vote is equal for all citizens.

For his time, the Constitution of 1936 year was very democratic, but the implementation of the rights and freedoms proclaimed in it was not provided for by the current legislation, the policy of mass repression carried out by the authorities was completely contrary to the basic legislation of the country.

In the place of conclusion, we can say that all the constitutions adopted before the independence of our state were in essence aimed at ensuring the Basic Law of the state, the state structure, the system of government and administration, the rights and freedoms of citizens, although in fact it was

⁴ Instructions on elections to the Soviets of the Uzbek SSR. ((With all changes and additions), Edition of the Central Election Commission of the USSR, 1929.

⁵ The "Stalinist" Constitution was adopted. [Electron Resource] Kirish tartibi: Presidential Library named after B.N. Yeltsin (prlib.ru)

originally the RSFSR, and later the constitutions adopted in the composition of the In this regard, the election campaigns of Soviets, which have been held almost every year since 1918 year, will serve as a base for attracting the citizens of the country to the construction of the state.

In the constitutions of the Soviet state, the exploitation of mankind and the destruction of a form of private ownership were identified as the main printsip for itself and considered the policy of deprivation of the right to elect for the implementation of these printsips. With this, the conscious of the population, having its own independent opinion and having initially limited all its rights to the category that could be opposed to colonial policy, subsequently achieved their destruction with the policy of repression.

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